

TABLE 1*

S. No.	X	Y	I		I		I		I		II		II	
			A COOC ₂ H ₅ M.P.°C	B CN Yield%	A CONH ₂ M.P.°C	B CN Yield%	A CN M.P.°C	B CN Yield%	A COCH ₃ M.P.°C	B COCH ₃ Yield%	A COCH ₃ M.P.°C	B COOC ₂ H ₅ Yield%		
1.	NO ₂	H	136-137	95	195	80	181	90	156	90	144	80		
2.	-do-	CH ₃	-do-	80	-do-	70	-do-	-do-	-do-	85	-do-	-do-	75	
3.	-do-	Cl	-do-	90	-do-	80	-do-	-do-	-do-	85	-do-	-do-	85	I
4.	H	-do-	117-118	80	162	70	128	80	104	75	79	70		
5.	-do-	H	-do-	70	-do-	60	-do-	-do-	-do-	80	-do-	-do-	65	

*All the melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 2

$$o\text{-XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}=\overset{\text{A}}{\underset{\text{B}}{\text{C}}}$$

I

X=NO₂

and

$$o\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}=\overset{\text{(a)}}{\text{CH}}-\overset{\text{(b)}}{\text{CH}}-\overset{\text{(c)}}{\text{CH}}-\overset{\text{A}}{\underset{\text{B}}{\text{CH}}}-\overset{\text{A}}{\underset{\text{B}}{\text{CH}}}$$

II

S. No.	A	B	IR Spectra		$\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}(\text{cm}^{-1})$	NMR Spectra $\delta_{\text{CDCl}_3}^{\text{TMS}}(\tau)$	Mol. Formula	Elemental Analysis		
			C=N	C=O				Found%	Cald. %	
I										
1.	CN	CN	2220 2200	—	982	1.87, (H _c), d, 2.70, (H _a), d, 2.82, (H _b), q,	C ₁₂ H ₇ N ₃ O ₃	C H N	63.8 3.3 18.5	63.9 3.1 18.6
2.	CN	COOC ₂ H ₅	2226	1724	995 952	1.60-3.00, m, (7H, 4H-arom. & 3H-a, b & c.)	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄	C H N	61.9 4.4 10.1	61.8 4.4 10.3
3.	CN	CONH ₂	2210	—	975 955	—	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₃ O ₃	C H N	58.9 3.9 16.9	59.2 3.7 17.2
4.	COCH ₃	COCH ₃	—	1692	980 963	1.68-3.20, m, (7H, arom. and a, b & c.)	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ NO ₄	C H N	64.9 4.9 5.6	64.8 5.0 5.4
II										
5.	COCH ₃	COOC ₂ H ₅	—	1734 1708 1700	972	7.02, d(H _c) 7.41, s(H _d) & (H _e).	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ NO ₃	C H N	60.2 6.0 3.0	60.1 6.0 3.3

The products have been characterized by their melting and mixed melting points; elemental and spectral analysis. The infrared spectra show bands in the region 995-952 cm⁻¹ for the CH=CH trans function showing thereby that the original trans configuration of the styrene moiety remains unaffected. IR bands in the region 2226-2200 cm⁻¹ show the presence of -C≡N, in the region 1734-1692 cm⁻¹ of a C=O (ester and keto), and at 3476 cm⁻¹ of an N-H (amide). Absorption at 1520-1510 and 1355-1343 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of a nitro group. The nuclear magnetic resonance spectra also give satisfactory analysis for the structures assigned to the adducts. The results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Experimental

A typical procedure used for these reactions is described here.

Nitron (0.01 mole) was taken into a 50 ml standard joint conical flask containing dry benzene (15 ml). The contents of the flask were warmed to get a homogeneous solution to which was added an equivalent amount of the active methylene compound (2 mole equivalents in the case of ethyl acetoacetate) and a few drops of piperidine as catalyst. The flask was stoppered, the contents were vigorously shaken for ten minutes and allowed to stand at room temperature. When the product

separated out, it was filtered, dried and recrystallized. The data for these adducts are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

For mixed melting point determination authentic samples were obtained by condensing equimolar quantities of the active methylene compounds and the respective aldehydes using a few drops of piperidine as catalyst. Two molar excess of ethyl acetoacetate was used in this case also. Ethanol was used for recrystallization in all cases. Use of excess of active methylene compounds gives the same results.

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References

- G. E. UTZINGER and F. A. REGENASS., *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1954, 37, 1892.
- H. STAM and J. HOENICKE., *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1971, 748, 143.
- N. SINGH and K. KRISHAN., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 884.